

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF USING VIDEO CONTENT IN TEACHING COLLOCATIONS IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *The article advocates for the application of video content in EFL classrooms in universities as a potent tool to teach collocations by highlighting the setbacks the process of teaching collocations comes with as well as the effects of video content integration as a solution. The primary purpose of the study is to explore the effectiveness of utilizing video content in teaching collocations in developing EFL learners' productive skills. The article discusses the views of different researchers on the issue of using video content to teach collocations, the classification of collocations, the obstacles EFL teachers face in teaching collocations, and the positive effects of integrating video content in this process.*

Аннотация. *В статье пропагандируется применение видеоконтента в классах английского языка в университетах в качестве мощного инструмента для обучения словосочетаниям, подчеркивая препятствия, с которыми сталкивается процесс обучения словосочетаниям, а также эффекты интеграции видеоконтента в качестве решения. Основная цель исследования — изучить эффективность использования видеоконтента при обучении словосочетаниям и развитии продуктивных навыков учащихся английского языка. В статье рассматриваются взгляды разных исследователей на проблему использования видеоконтента для обучения словосочетаниям, классификацию словосочетаний, препятствия, с которыми сталкиваются преподаватели английского языка при обучении словосочетаниям, а также положительные эффекты интеграции видеоконтента в этот процесс.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada universitetlardagi chet tili sinflarida video kontentni ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini o'rgatish uchun kuchli vosita sifatida qo'llash, ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini o'rganish jarayoni duch keladigan to'siqlarni, shuningdek, video kontentni yechim sifatida integratsiyalashuv ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi chet tili organuvchi talabalarining ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini o'rgatish va samarali ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda video kontentdan foydalanish samaradorligini o'rganishdir. Maqolada turli tadqiqotchilarning ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini o'rgatish uchun video kontentdan foydalanish haqidagi qarashlari, ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini tasniflash, ingliz tili o'qituvchilariga ingliz tili kollokatsiyalarini o'rgatishda duch keladigan to'siqlar va video kontentni ushbu jarayonga integratsiyalashning ijobiy ta'siri haqidagi qarashlari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Keywords: *collocations, video content, ICT, multiple-word units, lexical proficiency.*

Ключевые слова: *коллокации, видеоконтент, ИКТ, многословные единицы, знание лексики.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kollokatsiyalar, video kontent, AKT, ko'p so'zli birliklar, leksik kompetensiya.*

The paramount role of vocabulary learning and teaching has gained momentum in EFL teaching in the recent three decades since learners' lexical proficiency may prompt native-like language learning. However, this very aspect of the English language was hugely undervalued in

teaching English until that due to the continuous dominance of grammar. According to Carter and McCarthy (1998), Nation (1990), and Zimmerman (1997), not only vocabulary learning and teaching were not prioritized by researchers and curriculum developers but also not greatly downgraded in the past. Yet, the situation altered in favor of vocabulary teaching and learning when researchers and curriculum developers recognized the fundamental significance it holds (Coady and Huckin, 1997; Griffiths, 2003; Shen, 2008). The idea of accuracy being more important than fluency, that's to say, teaching grammar being prioritized compared to vocabulary teaching, has been eliminated because recipients may ignore grammatical faults when the message is presented clearly (Jordens & Lalleman, 1996). In fact, according to research by Huda Suleiman (2022), lexical errors are considered more serious by native speakers and meant to impede comprehension compared to grammatical ones. In other words, although the speech has some grammatical errors that do not hinder the overall meaning it intends to convey, successful communication may occur with the correct use of lexical items. This, in turn, demonstrates the role of vocabulary teaching and lexical proficiency in language learning and teaching.

Lexical competence is another crucial component of L2 academic proficiency. While a huge amount of attention is given to exploring how to teach and learn individual words, collocations as part of multi-word units have only recently gained momentum in EFL contexts. As has been claimed by Schmitt (2010), collocations are proposed to be a requirement for reaching advanced levels of fluency and language proficiency in second language (L2) learning. It is predominantly due to the fact that collocations assist in making speech more natural. However, collocations, not always following a clear logic and having an arbitrary nature, pose specific challenges in comparison to single words. Pallicer-Sanchez (2017) noted that L2 learners acquire multiple-word units less quickly than single-word acquisition. Using collocations and other multiple-word units appropriately is another major issue in L2 learning.

One of the few problematic things about collocations is that different researchers hold different perspectives on differentiating them into types. While Hill (2000) defined collocations as consisting of two or more elements as well as following some patterns, Lewis's (1998) categorization of collocation is short and simple. Hill (2000) suggested that collocations follow several patterns incorporating two or more words:

Adjective + Noun	A close friend
Noun + Noun	A board game
Verb + Adjective + Noun	Learn a foreign language
Verb + Adverb	Walk softly
Adverb + Verb	Closely examine
Adverb + Adjective	Heavily influenced
Verb + Preposition + Noun	Filled with awe

Lewis (1998), however, presents a more straightforward classification of collocations: strong, weak, and medium. According to Lewis (1998), strong collocations are the ones whose elements are heavily connected with each other. The example presented for this very category is *rancid butter* as the word “rancid” can only be utilized in relation to butter. The next category is weak collocations which are explained to be co-occurring more frequently than randomly. Additionally, there should be a more predictable pattern in this category to become collocations:

red or white wine. The collocations whose elements co-occur more frequently than weak collocations are presented as medium-strength collocations e.g., *to carry out research*. Tanju A mere introduction to collocations in the EFL classroom is not sufficient since the learners should be introduced to the contexts where and when to use them, and the level of formality that collocation holds. Deveci (2004) argues that the context in which a collocation is used holds the utmost importance considering the fact that some collocations are applicable in certain contexts. Hence, Deveci (2004) argues that “knowledge of connotation and formality” is critical in selecting which collocation to use.

Learning and teaching collocations is not as straightforward a task in practice as may have been given in theory. The application of the most novel pedagogical or innovative practices may not generate the desired results due to several reasons such as the random nature of collocations, negative L1 transfer, and a huge volume of collocations to deal with. One of the most apparent difficulties in teaching collocations happens due to the arbitrary nature of collocations. Lewis (1997) explained it as “the choice of the constituent words does not follow any logic, but is only based on the linguistic convention”. Another important moment regarding teaching collocations comes from the fact that the learners are heavily influenced by their L1 while using collocations. According to Mahmoud (2005), most inaccuracies in collocations are explained by influence from the mother tongue. In other words, when learners are unsure about the correct collocation in the target language, they often look for a comparable expression in their mother tongue. Learning new words is a tough job not even mentioning the fact that some words are only linked with certain ones. Even though learning and teaching collocations is a time-consuming and arduous process, Roberto De Caro (2009) suggests EFL learners be ready for the task of dealing with collocations owing to their frequent use in both written and spoken English.

The ultimate goal of EFL teachers is to analyze the teaching context and find the most effective method to eliminate potential setbacks in teaching collocations. EFL teachers and learners now have access to and opportunity to connect with a wide range of teaching and learning sources and resources in online spaces to strengthen learners` lexical proficiency thanks to the advancement and popularity of information and communication technologies (ICT). With the rise of social media and networking apps, using ICT to support vocabulary teaching and learning has become more popular recently. The application of social media and networking sites in L2 classes not only builds motivation and self-learning but also facilitates information access (Yunus et al., 2012). One of the few aspects of using social media platforms as well as the Internet worthwhile in EFL contexts is the fact that they provide multimedia resources. Students not only can be active on social media platforms and websites but also are exposed to many sorts of digital texts, audio, and videos. The research by Kurniawati, Maolida, and Anjaniputra (2018) concluded that 72,9% percent of pupils use digital media every day. Digital media utilization in the classroom is unquestionably beneficial for EFL teachers looking for the most effective teaching strategy, particularly when teaching multiple-word units.

Despite the numerous types of media formats provided by social media and the Internet, selecting one appropriate format to be used in the EFL classroom produces more effective results. Recent years brought the prominence of video materials to be applied in EFL classrooms caused by the daily exposure of learners to videos on social media platforms and Internet websites in the form of shorts, reels, etc. EFL teachers are, hence, using them as authentic materials to facilitate collocation learning. Conventional approaches to teaching collocations, such as rote memorization and decontextualized activities, sometimes fall short in terms of

student engagement and meaningful language usage context. With its captivating methods of teaching multiple-word units in context, video materials have become a potent instrument in language instruction in recent years. Videos, including instructional content, Instagram reels, and YouTube shorts offer rich meaningful input that demonstrates how collocations are employed naturally in written and spoken conversations. Webb and Rodgers (2016) reported that audiovisual resources offer both context and meaningful exposure for collocations to be ingrained in long-term memory. In other words, when opposed to conventional text-based methods, simultaneous exposure of visual and audio input assists students in connecting words in context, improving the learning process.

In conclusion, video content is essential for teaching university students collocations, as scientific study continuously shows. Videos are a potent tool for language acquisition because of their multimodal nature, contextualized learning, and motivational boost.

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